

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OPEJO****FIRST NAME: PIUS****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8.1

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15-23)
3. American Versus British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44-50)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1) INTRODUCTION

Postgraduate study requires a very high commitment amidst many other competing priorities. Although many people in this era aspire to pursue a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) degree, many still need to decide. Besides the financial concern, most potential students contemplate when to start and their prospects. Is it a must to have a doctoral degree? Which Ph.D. is the most suitable, and which university is the best to undertake? I found myself in a similar situation a few months ago. I searched for more information about my interests within the medical field. I read various websites, journals, and books and interacted with senior professionals in academia. Upon being convinced, I enrolled for a Ph.D. in Bioethics at one of the prestigious intergovernmental universities, EUCLID University, formed under the United Nations treaty.

As part of the initial student orientation program, I understood that EUCLID University emphasizes quality, integrity, and timeliness in its study programs. The first

period for the inaugural module, ACA-401D (period 1), was deliberately chosen to usher in postgraduate students to understand and master the gist of academic writing. The study material delved deeper into writing a good academic essay, punctuation, variants of English (American Vs. British), plagiarism, and writing style and guide. A more profound understanding of these topics will make my academic journey at EUCLID enjoyable.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Good academic essay writing skills are indispensable attributes of postgraduate study. Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program, in particular, demands excellence in mastering the art of academic essay writing. Moreover, writing research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork should not be fictional. It should aim to communicate new ideas or contribute additional information to what is already known (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-14).

At EUCLID, all modules require writing essays in the form of response papers, major papers, and quiz papers. The guidelines provided during initial student orientation are beneficial as a reference during ongoing writing. The expert faculty explicitly outlined a step-by-step approach to this topic, giving suitable examples. A student should write an essay as a response paper and structure it in four parts. Furthermore, they should summarize critical concepts of the particular study material provided and detail their reactions to specific concepts (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 2-4). The outline provided is straightforward, making a logical flow of information concise. If such an outline is not given to the students, some will end up with a forest of words but a desert of points.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Unless punctuations are applied appropriately, the essay may not make sense to the reader. Reading an essay should be like listening to a smoothly flowing news broadcast on a radio station. This flow of information can be made possible for the reader when good punctuation is applied. Proper punctuation in essay writing is as good as using an appropriate route map when navigating unfamiliar routes. It helps one know when to pause or even stop.

Generally, using as little punctuation as necessary is advisable while retaining the sentence's meaning (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 15-23). I agree with this statement because the more punctuation used, the more complex and confusing the essay will read

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

English is widely used in the world today. Most countries use English as an official communication language, while most academic and professional bodies use it for instruction. However, due to other indigenous languages and with the current mobility of

humans, English has undergone several adulterations. Examples include the West African Penguin English and the Nairobi City colloquial English, among others. Despite the many variants of the English language, most people generally prefer to use either American or British English.

At the beginning of the course pack (period 1) study material, emphasis was placed on mastering the English variant and consistently using it while writing academic essays. Important to note is that a student should use either U.S. or U.K. English, but the entire document should adopt one chosen variant of English. According to Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma, it is clear that since World War II, American English has grown steadily in international significance. The scholars attribute this growth to the parallel development of America's worldwide economic, political, technological, and cultural influence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-32). Whereas my country, Uganda, predominantly used British English in schools and offices because of its historical past, I now believe that American English has surpassed its global dominance. It is, therefore, imperative to understand the guidelines for using American English.

5) PLAGIARISM

This terminology has always surfaced whenever I get to read journal papers. Understanding the term "plagiarism" should be clear to every scholar or writer. According to Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma (2021, 34), "Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information." As a student of Bioethics, this is one thing that I vehemently condemn. Understanding how and when to properly and appropriately cite articles will go a long way in improving my writing skills. It will also help me in the future when reviewing other writers' work and mentoring aspiring writers to avoid this malpractice.

6) STYLE GUIDE

Although writing may take a particular direction, such as technical, commercial, or business, journalism, and web copywriting, it is essential to be consistent with a chosen style. EUCLID recommends using Chicago Rules (Turabian) style and American English. Other internationally recognized styles and British English are also acceptable (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41). I understand that to communicate effectively through any channel, being clear and consistent is a must. Even if I prefer a particular style or English in writing, some companies or organizations may dictate a specific style and English that is coherent and consistent with their publishing. In such cases, I have to understand and adopt their standard of practice if I intend to submit to them. Most publishing companies usually provide a style guide that lists several accepted specifications in writing, such as manuscript layout, font usage, symbols and abbreviations, and terminology.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE (CMS)

Like there are different publishing companies and media houses, other writing styles exist. At EUCLID, the recommended style is the Chicago style, which is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the *Chicago Manual of Style* (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 1996, which are both published by the university of Chicago press (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 44). I am unfamiliar with this writing style, but I will understand and apply it appropriately with more reading and practice. Reading through this section of the study material has awakened me to the need for a detailed understanding of how to write a good research paper, correctly using abbreviations and acronyms, italics, capitalization, compound words and quotation marks, numbers, and page formatting.

It became clear to me that whereas the *Chicago Manual of Style* focuses on book publishing, Turabian's *Manual for Writers* is the official guide to applying the Chicago style to manuscripts (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 50). This information is an eye-opener as I plan to start writing during my long academic career at EUCLID. I now understand the difference between book publishing and research paper writing for manuscripts.

8) CONCLUSION

A famous adage states, "A journey of a thousand miles starts with a step." Similarly, my journey in this Ph.D. program started with this ACA-401D (period 1) course pack. Even with some exposure to academic writing, I must admit that a lot is yet to learn. To become an excellent academic writer, and besides fulfilling the requirements for this study program, EUCLID has provided me with detailed study material strategically allocated at the beginning of the course. I now must digest it and appropriately apply it in the future. The topic of plagiarism, others notwithstanding, directly touches my pivotal interest in ethics. As I strive to understand Zotero and Grammarly software better, I should also do my best to avoid plagiarism and practice EUCLID's acceptable writing standards. I will improve my writing skills with subsequent response papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper at EUCLID*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.